

DELAMINATION OF LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO MECHANICAL AND HYGROTHERMAL LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

Potential energy release rates associated with delaminations at free edge and transverse crack tip in laminate under mechanical and hygrothermal loadings are analyzed by the superposition method. Transforming the original free edge and matrix crack problems with mechanical and hygrothermal loadings to those with mechanical tractions applied on the free edge and matrix crack surfaces, we can clarify the effect of the hygrothermal loading on the energy release rates.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most commonly observed failure modes in the continuous fiber reinforced composite laminates subjected to mechanical, thermal and hygroscopic loadings is delamination at the free edge or matrix crack tip. The onset and growth of the delamination can be characterized by the fracture mechanics based on the potential energy release rate.

The potential energy release rate for the free edge delamination of laminates under the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings was obtained by O'Brien [1] based on the stiffness change due to the delamination growth while it was analyzed by Kondo and Aoki [2] utilizing the superposition method. The potential energy release rate for the delamination at the tip of 90° ply matrix crack was obtained by O'Brien [3] based on the compliance change due to the delamination growth while it was analyzed by Kondo [4] utilizing the superposition method. And O'Brien [5] analyzed the potential energy release rate for the delamination at the tip of angle ply matrix crack.

In the present paper, the superposition method is applied to obtain the potential energy release rate for the delamination at the tip of angle ply matrix crack as well as at the tip of cross ply matrix crack. By analyzing the laminates subjected to the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings with gradient through the thickness, the influence of the thermal and hygroscopic expansions on the delaminations at the free edge and transverse crack tip is clarified.

SUPERPOSITION METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF INTERLAMINAR STRESSES

We consider a laminate subjected to uniform mechanical and hygrothermal loadings with the

gradient through thickness. First, we obtain a uniform stress distribution in an infinite laminate without free edge and transverse crack based on the classical lamination theory. Then, by utilizing the superposition method, we analyze the interlaminar stresses at the free edge of a semi-infinite laminate as shown in Fig.1, and those at the tips of a transverse crack in an angle ply of an infinite laminate as shown in Fig.2.

Figure 1. Free Edge of Semi-infinite Laminate

Figure 2. Transverse Crack in Angle Ply of Infinite Laminate

INPLANE STRESSES IN INFINITE LAMINATE

The stress-strain relationship for each unidirectional lamina in the laminate is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{10} \\ \epsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 correspond to the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively, of a zero-degree ply and the initial strains due to the temperature change ΔT and moisture content change ΔM are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{10} \\ \epsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Delta T + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Delta M \quad (2)$$

where α_i and β_i are the thermal and hygroscopic expansion coefficients, respectively. The inverse relationship of Eqn (1) in the laminate coordinates is written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{x0} \\ \epsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

For an infinite laminate subjected to the uniform mechanical loading such as the generalized stresses N_x , N_y , N_{xy} , M_x , M_y and M_{xy} , and the uniform hygrothermal loading such as the temperature and moisture content changes given by

$$\Delta T = \Delta T_0 + \Delta T_1 z \quad \Delta M = \Delta M_0 + \Delta M_1 z \quad (4)$$

the strains in each lamina are expressed in terms of the generalized strains as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + z \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

which coincide with the Kirchoff hypothesis employed in the classical lamination theory [6]. Substituting Eqn (4) into Eqn (2) and dividing the initial strains into the isotropic and deviatoric parts, we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{10} \\ \varepsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (\Delta\theta_0 + \Delta\theta_1 z) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (\Delta\theta'_0 + \Delta\theta'_1 z) \quad (6)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\theta_0 \\ \Delta\theta_1 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta T_0 \\ \Delta T_1 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\beta_1 + \beta_2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta M_0 \\ \Delta M_1 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\theta'_0 \\ \Delta\theta'_1 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta T_0 \\ \Delta T_1 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\beta_1 - \beta_2}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta M_0 \\ \Delta M_1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

and, therefore,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \varepsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (\Delta\theta_0 + \Delta\theta_1 z) + \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\theta \\ -\cos 2\theta \\ 2 \sin 2\theta \end{bmatrix}_k (\Delta\theta'_0 + \Delta\theta'_1 z) \quad (8)$$

Substituting Eqn (5) and (8) into Eqn (3), we have the stresses in each lamina as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \left(\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + z \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} (\Delta\theta_0 + \Delta\theta_1 z) + \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\theta \\ -\cos 2\theta \\ 2 \sin 2\theta \end{bmatrix}_k (\Delta\theta'_0 + \Delta\theta'_1 z) \right) \quad (9)$$

The generalized stresses of the laminate are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ z\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k dz \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eqn (9) into Eqn (10), we have the constitutive equation for the laminate as

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_x \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{x0} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{y0} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{x0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{y0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{x0} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{y0} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{x0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{y0} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\theta_0 \\ \Delta\theta_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$+ \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} A'_{11} & A'_{12} & A'_{16} & B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} \\ A'_{12} & A'_{22} & A'_{26} & B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} \\ A'_{16} & A'_{26} & A'_{66} & B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} \\ B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} & D'_{11} & D'_{12} & D'_{16} \\ B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} & D'_{12} & D'_{22} & D'_{26} \\ B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} & D'_{16} & D'_{26} & D'_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\theta'_0 \\ \Delta\theta'_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$A_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} dz \quad B_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} z dz \quad D_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} z^2 dz \quad (13)$$

and, in Eqn (12)

$$\begin{bmatrix} A'_{11} & A'_{12} & A'_{16} & B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} \\ A'_{12} & A'_{22} & A'_{26} & B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} \\ A'_{16} & A'_{26} & A'_{66} & B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} \\ B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} & D'_{11} & D'_{12} & D'_{16} \\ B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} & D'_{12} & D'_{22} & D'_{26} \\ B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} & D'_{16} & D'_{26} & D'_{66} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ z\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\theta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\cos 2\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\sin 2\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & z\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (14)$$

From Eqns (9) and (11), we have the stresses in each lamina as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ z\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{zI} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} A'_{11} & A'_{12} & A'_{16} & B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} \\ A'_{12} & A'_{22} & A'_{26} & B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} \\ A'_{16} & A'_{26} & A'_{66} & B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} \\ B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} & D'_{11} & D'_{12} & D'_{16} \\ B'_{12} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} & D'_{12} & D'_{22} & D'_{26} \\ B'_{16} & B'_{26} & B'_{66} & D'_{16} & D'_{26} & D'_{66} \end{bmatrix} \right. \\
 & - \left. \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\theta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\cos 2\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \sin 2\theta \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{zI} \end{bmatrix} \right\} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\theta'_0 \\ \Delta\theta'_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

We can see that the stresses due to the hygrothermal loading are expressed in terms of only $\Delta\theta'_0$ and $\Delta\theta'_1$.

SUPERPOSITION METHOD

We analyze the interlaminar stresses in the vicinity of the free edge or transverse crack tip of the laminate subjected to the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings by the superposition method [2, 4, 7].

Figure 3. Superposition Method for Analysis of Interlaminar Stresses at Free Edge of Semi-infinite Laminate

To obtain a semi-infinite laminate with a straight edge, we make a fictitious cut along the plane of $y = 0$ in the infinite laminate subjected to the prescribed loadings as shown in Fig.3(a). Then, as shown in Fig.3(b), we apply tractions which are of the same magnitude but of opposite sign to those on the cut in Fig.3(a) to a straight edge of a semi-infinite laminate without any loadings. The superposition of the load system of Fig.3(a) to that of Fig.3(b) gives a semi-infinite laminate with a free edge subjected to the prescribed loadings as presented in Fig.3(c). Since the load system of Fig.3(a) gives no interlaminar stresses, the configuration of Fig.3(b) yields the interlaminar stresses identical to those in the free edge problem of Fig.3(c). Therefore, the edge traction problem of Fig.3(b) represents the transformed free edge problem. It should be noted that, even if there exist the delaminations in the infinite laminate, the stresses are given by the classical lamination theory. Consequently, a laminate with edge delaminations can also be

analyzed the superposition method.

Figure 4. Superposition Method for Analysis of Interlaminar Stresses at Transverse Crack Tip of Infinite Laminate

To obtain an infinite laminate with angle ply transverse crack, we make a fictitious cut along the plane of $y = \tan \theta x$ in the angle ply of the infinite plane subjected to the prescribed loadings as shown in Fig.4(a). Then, as shown in Fig.4(b), we apply tractions which are of the same magnitude but of opposite sign to those on the cut in Fig.4(a) to a transverse crack surface in an infinite laminate without any loadings. The superposition of the load system of Fig.4(a) to that of Fig.4(b) gives an infinite laminate with free transverse crack surface subjected to the prescribed loadings as shown in Fig.4(c). Therefore, the configuration of Fig.4(b) represents the transformed transverse crack problem.

POTENTIAL ENERGY RELEASE RATE

For the transformed free edge and transverse crack problems, the potential energy release rate G associated with the delamination growth da is written as

$$G = -\frac{d\Pi}{da} = \frac{dU}{da} \tag{16}$$

where Π and U is the potential energy and the strain energy, respectively. Since the strain energy increase dU due to the delamination growth da can be obtained from the tractions applied to the free edge and transverse crack surface in the transformed problems, the potential energy release rate can be calculated from Eqn (16).

For the free edge delamination as shown in Fig.5, we can get the generalized stresses N_y , N_{xy} and M_y of the regions I, II_t and II_b in the corresponding infinite laminate from Eqn (15). We assume that

$$\epsilon_x = \kappa_x = \kappa_y = 0 \tag{17}$$

in the regions I, II_t and II_b in Fig.5 taking account of the constraint from the undelaminated region. Then, it follows from Eqn (16) that the potential energy release rate associated with the free edge delamination growth is given by

$$G = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{K=I, II, II_b} [N_y \quad N_{xy} \quad M_y]_K \begin{bmatrix} A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{22} \\ A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{26} \\ B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{22} \end{bmatrix}_K^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_y \end{bmatrix}_K \quad (18)$$

For the transverse crack tip delamination as shown in Fig.6, we can get the generalized stresses N_x , N_{xy} and M_x of the region I in the corresponding infinite laminate from Eqn (17). We assume that

$$\epsilon_y = \kappa_y = \kappa_{xy} = 0 \quad \epsilon_{xII} = \epsilon_{xII_b} \quad \gamma_{xyII} = \gamma_{xyII_b} \quad \kappa_{xII} = \kappa_{xII_b} \quad (19)$$

in the regions I, II and II_b in Fig.6 considering the constraint from the undelaminated region. Then, it follows from Eqn (16) that the potential energy release rate associated with the transverse crack tip delamination growth is given by

$$G = \frac{1}{4} [N_x \quad N_{xy} \quad M_x]_I \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{16} & B_{11} \\ A_{16} & A_{66} & B_{16} \\ B_{11} & B_{16} & D_{11} \end{bmatrix}_I + \left[\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{16} & B_{11} \\ A_{16} & A_{66} & B_{16} \\ B_{11} & B_{16} & D_{11} \end{bmatrix}_{II} + \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{16} & B_{11} \\ A_{16} & A_{66} & B_{16} \\ B_{11} & B_{16} & D_{11} \end{bmatrix}_{II_b} \right]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \end{bmatrix}_I \quad (20)$$

Figure 5. Transformed Free Edge Problem of Laminate with Edge Delamination

Figure 6. Transformed Transverse Crack Problem of Laminate with Transverse Crack Tip Delamination

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 7 shows the contour plots of the potential energy release rate for graphite-epoxy $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminate under the membrane load N_x and the temperature and moisture content changes uniform through the thickness ΔT_0 and ΔM_0 where $N_y = N_{xy} = M_x = M_y = M_{xy} = \Delta T_1 = \Delta M_1 = 0$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_{x0} = \{A_{22} / (A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2)\}N_x$. The contour lines of the energy release rates in the $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_{x0}$ and $\Delta T_0 + \{(\beta_1 - \beta_2) / (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\}\Delta M_0$ plane are ellipses in general and are parallel lines when the length of the major axis becomes infinite. It can be seen from Eqns (15), (18) and (20) that the potential energy release rates are expressed in terms of the mechanical loads N_x , N_y , N_{xy} , M_x , M_y and M_{xy} and the hygrothermal expansions $\Delta \Theta'_0$ and $\Delta \Theta'_1$. Therefore, in Fig.7, the energy

release rates are expressed in terms of $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_{x0}$ and $\Delta T_0 + \{(\beta_1 - \beta_2)/(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\}\Delta M_0$.

Figure 7. Contour Plots of Potential Energy Release Rates for Delaminations at Free Edge and Transverse Crack Tip of Graphite-Epoxy $[45^\circ/45^\circ]_s$ Laminate under Membrane Load N_x and Temperature and Moisture Content Changes ΔT_0 and ΔM_0 .

CONCLUSIONS

Utilizing the superposition method, the potential energy release rates associated with delamination growth at the free edge and transverse crack tip of laminates subjected to the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings were obtained. It was found that the potential energy release rates due to the hygrothermal expansions are expressed in terms of the deviatoric hygrothermal expansions $\Delta\theta'_0$ and $\Delta\theta'_1$.

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